

PRINCIPLES OF VOCATIONAL DIRECTION OF YOUTH IN US EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article provides information about the educational system of the United States, the orientation of young people to the profession. The conditions created for the education of young people and their place in the life of young people, and the attention paid to the education of young generations in the development of every society and their rise to the top are highlighted.

Key words: school, education, educational courses, program, developed countries, kindergarten, elementary school, public education, American colloquial speech.

Introduction:

Introduction: All states in the United States have compulsory education laws for children between the ages of five or eight to ten or eighteen, depending on the state. The curriculum may vary from state to state and school district, but all states are required by law to ensure that public school students meet the required minimum educational standards.

Higher education institutions vary greatly in terms of the quality of education. The 8 Ivy League universities are among the most prestigious universities in the United States and around the world. As of 2010, the United States had the 10th highest percentage of college-educated adults among industrialized nations. The US literacy rate is 99% (2008), and in 2011, 46% of those aged 25 and over had a high school diploma, and 30% had a bachelor's degree. The main language of education is English. At about 5 years old, American children go to elementary school (*English: elementary school*), zero grade (*German: kindergarten*). In many states, zero grade is optional.

However, almost all American children attend kindergarten. Although Kindergarten literally means "kindergarten" in German, in the United States, kindergartens exist separately and are literally called preschools. Elementary school lasts until the fifth or sixth grade (*depending on the school district*), after which the student goes to middle school (*English: middle school*), ending with the eighth or ninth grade, respectively.

High school (*English: highschool*) is grades nine through twelfth, so Americans usually finish high school at age 18. Those with a high school diploma

can attend community colleges. In statistics, such educational institutions are called two-year colleges (two-year colleges), other names are also widespread: English: community college, small college, technical college or city college. These institutions give a scientific degree after two years of study (English: associate's degree).

Comparable to secondary special education of the Russian Federation or apprentice (*apprentice*) or journeyman (journeyman) qualifications in a number of other countries, including Canada. But unlike the Russian Federation, where you can start studying at such an educational institution after the 9th grade, you can enter the US college only after completing secondary education.

Another option for continuing your education is to attend a college or university, where you can usually earn a bachelor's degree in four years. Those with a bachelor's degree can further study for a master's degree (2-3 years) or a PhD (3 years or more). Specially accredited faculties and universities (*post-graduate schools*) that require special preparation at the undergraduate level for admission award the degrees of doctor of medical sciences and doctor of jurisprudence.

Free public schools are primarily governed by democratically elected school boards, each of which has jurisdiction over a school district, often (but not always) bounded by a county or city. boundaries and includes one or more schools at each level. School boards determine school programs, hire teachers, and determine program funding.

States regulate education within their borders, set standards and exams for students. Public education is also publicly funded at various levels (*usually by the state*), but not included in school districts, not controlled by school boards, and other state regulations.

Most of the children study in public schools. For example, in 2013, about 87 percent of school-age children were educated in free public schools, about 10 percent in private schools, and 3 percent at home. However, using a non-registered free school in the US is prohibited, even if it appears to be "premium". Many private fee-paying schools are religious. The most widespread network of Catholic schools established by Irish immigrants in the second half of the 19th century. There are other private schools, often very expensive and sometimes highly competitive, to prepare students for admission to prestigious universities.

There are even online schools like Phillips Exeter Academy in New Hampshire that attract students from all over the country. About 3% of parents choose to homeschool their children for various reasons. In English, this is

debated as homeschooling (*home, a form of family education*). Some religious conservatives do not want their children to be taught ideas they disagree with, most commonly the theory of evolution. Others believe that their schools cannot meet the needs of their underachieving or otherwise gifted children.

From 2002-2003 to the 2003-2004 academic year, tuition fees in public higher education institutions increased by 14 percent, and in private higher education institutions by 6 percent, which is more than the rate of inflation during the same period. In American colloquial speech, all universities are usually called colleges (English: college), even though they are not colleges but universities.

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